

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OCHEN****FIRST NAME: ANTHONY MARK****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 06****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 14%

The author used MS Word 2013 on Windows 10.

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The steps involved in academic writing are not linear. However, some basic steps in writing an academic essay are needed. Tick some of the appropriate steps required before starting the essay.
 - Analyze the questions and define key terms, introduce the topic, establish the points of view, and draw conclusions.
 - Introduce the topic, establish the points of view, write the main body, and draw conclusions.
 - Research the topic, write the main body, establish the points of view, and draw conclusions.

- Analyze the question and define key terms, establish the points of view, research the topic, and take notes from your preliminary reading.**¹
2. What is the recommended citation style used by the EUCLID University?
- Author-date-style.
 - Non-bibliography style.
 - Chicago rules (Turabian style).**²
 - APA style.
3. Mention some of the essential data sources used in the research field.
- University, tertiary, secondary, and primary data sources.
 - Tertiary, secondary, and primary data sources.**³
 - Secondary, tertiary, university, and primary data sources.
 - Primary, secondary, tertiary, and university data sources.
4. A research argument is like a conversation with a community of receptive but skeptical colleagues. Please mention some of the elements of a research argument you know of.
- A claim and reasons.**⁴

¹ Laurent Cleenwerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C: Euclid University Press, 2024), 8.

² Ibid., 41.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 35.

⁴ Ibid., 58.

- A hypothesis.
 - Research questions.
 - None of the above.
5. Dissertation research is a collaborative process primarily involving students and other stakeholders. Mention the stakeholders involved in a student's dissertation research.
- Relatives.
 - Main professors and supervisory research team members.**⁵
 - a) and b).
 - None of the above.
6. Conducting dissertation research involves preparing ideally two documents. Choose the two documents.
- Dissertation concept paper and dissertation prospectus.
 - Dissertation prospects and dissertation manuscript.
 - Dissertation prospects and dissertation.**⁶
 - Dissertation and dissertation manuscript.
7. Both qualitative and quantitative researchers acknowledge that potential for bias exists in research, and there are various sources of potential bias in dissertation research. Mention some of the sources of the biases.

⁵ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 8.

⁶ Ibid., 9.

- Experience bias.
- Population bias.
- a) and b).**⁷
- None of the above.

8. How many WHO geographical regions exist in the whole world?

- Eight WHO regions.
- Ten WHO regions.
- Six WHO regions.**⁸
- Seven WHO regions.

9. Tick the correct answer to the following statements.

- An abbreviation is a shortened form of a word.**⁹
- An acronym is a shortened form of a phrase.
- PDF is an example of an abbreviation.
- DNA is an example of an acronym.

⁷ Ibid., 15.

⁸ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, Second Edition (Copenhagen: WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2013), 11.

⁹ Ibid., 19.

10. What is the generic order and format of dissertation chapters?

- Introduction; literature review; methodology; findings; analysis, interpretations, and synthesis; conclusions and recommendations.**¹⁰
- Abstract, introduction, literature review, methods, findings, discussions, and conclusions.
- Research topic, abstract, introduction, literature review, methods, findings, discussions, and conclusions.
- Abstract, introduction, literature review, methods, findings, discussions, and recommendations.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition. Columbia University: Sage Publications. Inc, 2019.

Cleenwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C: Euclid University Press., 2024.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. Second Edition. Copenhagen: WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2013.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth Edition, Fourth Edition (Columbia University: Sage Publications. Inc, 2019), 73.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.